

ISic3400

I.Sicily inscription 3400

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

limestone; bronze

Object

pavement

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

Excavation of the 'decumanus maximus' 1999-2011

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 645618

Bibliography

Silvestrini, M. 2014. Nuove epigrafi da Lilibeo. In Zaccaria, C.(eds.), *L'Epigrafia dei porti. Atti della XVIIe rencontre sur l'épigraphie du monde romain, Aquileia, 14-16 ottobre 2010*. Trieste. pp. 207-226. At 215-220 no.3a fig.7-10

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